

EVALUATION OF ANTIPYRETIC POTENTIAL OF LAGHU MALINI VASANTA RASA –
A ZINC-CONTAINING HERBOMETALLIC PREPARATION IN YEAST-INDUCED
PYREXIA MODEL IN RATS¹*Dr. Manisha B. Walunj, ²Dr. Ankush H. Gunjal¹Associate Professor, Department of Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana SST Ayurved College Sangamner.²Professor, Department of Kayachikitsa SMBT Ayurved College Nashik.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Manisha B. Walunj**

Associate Professor, Department of Rasa Shastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana SST Ayurved College Sangamner.

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ABSTRACT

Background Laghu Malini Vasanta Rasa (LMVR) is a classical herbometallic formulation widely indicated in Jwara (fever) in Ayurvedic texts. The formulation mainly comprises Yashada Bhasma (incinerated zinc) and Maricha (Piper nigrum Linn.) prepared with cow butter and lemon juice. **Objective:** To evaluate the antipyretic activity of Laghu Malini Vasanta Rasa in yeast-induced pyrexia in Wistar albino rats. **Materials and Methods:** The study was carried out after obtaining approval from the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC/12/2012/10). Pyrexia was induced by subcutaneous injection of 12.5% dried Brewer's yeast suspension (1 mL/100 g). Animals were divided into two groups (n = 6 each) Group I (Control) received vehicle, and Group II received LMVR (22.5 mg/kg, p.o.). Rectal temperature was recorded at baseline and at 3, 6, and 9 hours after drug administration. Data were expressed as Mean ± SEM and analyzed using Student's t-test, considering p 0.05 as statistically significant. **Results:** LMVR-treated rats showed a mild decrease in rectal temperature at 3 and 6 hours compared to the control group, though statistically insignificant (p > 0.05). At 9 hours, the formulation did not produce a temperature-lowering effect. **Conclusion:** Laghu Malini Vasanta Rasa demonstrated mild, non-significant antipyretic potential in yeast-induced pyrexia in rats. Its traditional use in Jwara may be attributed more to its Brimhana (anabolic) and Rasayana (rejuvenative) properties rather than to acute antipyretic action.

KEYWORDS: Laghu Malini Vasanta Rasa, Antipyretic activity, Yeast-induced pyrexia, Jwara.**INTRODUCTION**

Laghu Malini Vasanta Rasa (LMVR) is a classical Rasaushadhi mentioned in Rasa Paddhati (13th AD) [1] and other Ayurvedic texts including Rasayoga Sagar, [2] Yogaratnakara, [3] Vasavarajiyam, [4] and Rasa Chandanshu, [5] primarily indicated in the management of Jwara (fever). It is categorized under Kharaliya Rasayana group of Rasaushadhi and mainly comprises Yashada Bhasma (incinerated zinc) and Maricha (Piper nigrum Linn.) in a ratio of 21, with freshly prepared cow butter and lemon juice as Bhavana Dravya (levigation media).

Literary evidence suggests that the formulation exerts Brimhana (anabolic) and Rasayana (rejuvenative) effects

and may be particularly beneficial in Jeerna Jwara (chronic fever). Since most classical references describe its efficacy in Jwara, the present study was designed to experimentally assess its effect on body temperature regulation—specifically, to determine the antipyretic potential of LMVR using yeast-induced pyrexia in Wistar rats. [6]

MATERIALS AND METHODS**Ethical Approval**

The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC/12/2012/10), conducted as per CPCSEA guidelines.

Experimental Animals: Healthy Wistar albino rats of either sex, weighing 200 ± 20 g, were procured from the institutional animal house. Animals were housed in polypropylene cages (six per cage) with wheat husk bedding, maintained under standard laboratory conditions (12 h light/dark cycle, temperature $22 \pm 3^\circ\text{C}$, relative humidity 50–70%). They were fed Amrut brand rat pellets (Pranav Agro Ltd.) and water ad libitum. All

animals were acclimatized for 7 days before the experiment and fasted overnight prior to testing.

Test Drug

Laghu Malini Vasanta Rasa tablets were prepared as per Standard Manufacturing Procedure (SMP) developed for the formulation.^[7] The details of ingredients and their proportions are provided in Table 1.

Table no. 1: Details of ingredients of tablets of Laghu Malini Vasanta Rasa.

Drug	Part used	Botanical name	Proportion
<i>Yashada</i>	<i>Bhasma</i>	Incinerated zinc	Two parts
<i>Maricha</i>	Fruit	<i>Piper nigrum</i> Linn.	One part
<i>Navaneeta</i> (freshly prepared cow butter- levigating media)	-	Freshly prepared cow butter	50% of total quantity of ingredients
<i>Nimbu Toya</i> (lemon juice-levigating media)	Fruit	<i>Citrus acida</i> Linn.	q.s.(quantity sufficient)
<i>Pippali</i> as adjuvant	Fruit	<i>Piper logum</i> Linn.	In equal proportion to all ingredients
Honey as binding agent	-	-	30% of total mass ingredients

Raw materials were procured from the Pharmacy, Gujarat Ayurved University, Jamnagar, and authenticated in the Pharmacognosy Laboratory. *Yashada Bhasma* was prepared following classical methods *Shodhana* in lime water, *Jarana* using *Apamarga Panchanga*, and *Marana* with *Kumari Swarasa* as *Bhavana Dravya* until desired *Bhasma* characteristics were achieved (white with yellowish tint after five *Puti* at $\sim 650^\circ\text{C}$). Tablets (250 mg each) were prepared by wet granulation using honey as a binding agent and *Pippali* as adjuvant.

Dose Calculation and Administration

The human therapeutic dose (250 mg) was extrapolated to rat dose (22.5 mg/kg) based on the *Page and Barnes* (1964) body surface area conversion.^[8] LMVR and vehicle were administered orally using a gastric catheter attached to a syringe.

Experimental Design: Animals were divided into two groups (n = 6 each)

Group I – Control Vehicle only

Group II – Test (LMVR) 22.5 mg/kg orally

Baseline rectal temperatures were recorded. Pyrexia was induced by subcutaneous injection of 12.5% dried Brewer's yeast suspension (1 mL/100 g). LMVR or vehicle was administered one hour prior to yeast injection. Rectal temperatures were recorded at 3, 6, and 9 hours after drug administration. The change in rectal temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$) from baseline was calculated for each interval. Results are summarized in Table 2.

Statistical Analysis

Data were expressed as Mean \pm SEM and analyzed by Student's t-test (paired and unpaired). $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

After yeast injection, control group rats exhibited a consistent rise in rectal temperature at 3, 6, and 9 hours. LMVR-treated rats showed a mild decrease in temperature at 3 and 6 hours compared to control animals, but the difference was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). At 9 hours, LMVR failed to sustain the antipyretic effect. (table 2)

Table no. 2: Effect of Laghu Malini Vasanta Rasa on rectal temperature of pyrexia induced wister strain rats at 3 hours, 6 hours and 9 hours respectively.

Group	Dose mg/kg	Difference in rectal temperature at different time intervals ($^\circ\text{C}$)					
		After 3 h	% change	After 6 h	% change	After 9 h	% change
Control	-	0.98 ± 0.38	18.61↓	1.43 ± 0.37	6.99↓	1.52 ± 0.45	8.55↑
LMV	32.5	0.80 ± 0.45		1.33 ± 0.44		1.65 ± 0.17	

Data: MEAN \pm SEM, \uparrow increase, \downarrow decrease. (Unpaired 't' test)

DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to evaluate the antipyretic potential of Laghu Malini Vasanta Rasa through the yeast-induced pyrexia model. LMVR exhibited a mild reduction in rectal temperature at 3 and 6 hours, though

not statistically significant, suggesting limited antipyretic potential under the conditions studied.

Fever is a complex physiological response mediated by cytokines such as IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α , and interferons, which stimulate hypothalamic prostaglandin E₂ (PGE₂)

synthesis, elevating the thermal set point.^[9] Conventional antipyretics act primarily via inhibition of cyclooxygenase and reduction of hypothalamic PGE₂ levels. In this study, the mild temperature-lowering effect of LMVR could be attributed to its ingredients. *Yashada Bhasma* (Zinc complex) Zinc is known to influence immune and inflammatory responses, with studies showing modulation of cytokine production.^[10] Piperine, an alkaloid present in *Piper nigrum* and *Piper longum*, has been reported to possess antipyretic, analgesic, and anti-inflammatory activities.^[11]

The non-significant outcome might be due to lower bioavailability, insufficient duration, or dosage. LMVR's traditional use in *Jwara* may relate more to its *Brimhana* and *Rasayana* actions, supporting recovery and immune modulation rather than direct antipyretic activity.

Future investigations should explore higher or repeated doses, Inclusion of a standard antipyretic reference drug, Biochemical analysis of cytokine and PGE₂ modulation, Structural identification of zinc–piperine complexes for mechanistic insights.

CONCLUSION

Laghu Malini Vasanta Rasa, a zinc-based herbometallic formulation indicated in *Jwara*, exhibited mild, non-significant antipyretic activity in yeast-induced pyrexia in rats. The results suggest a possible supportive rather than primary antipyretic role. Further pharmacological and analytical studies are warranted to elucidate its mechanism of action and clinical relevance.

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